

ON THE MOVING BOUNDARY METHOD FOR THE DETERMINATION OF ABSOLUTE RATES OF MIGRATION AND TRANSPORT NUMBERS OF IONS.

By N. C. SEN-GUPTA.

In the present paper the influence of the concentration of indicator ions on the absolute velocity and transport number of chloride, nitrate and sulphate ions has been investigated in centinormal solutions with Mukherjee's cataphoretic apparatus (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1922, **A103**, 102). The concentration adjustments behind a moving boundary have been followed with the same apparatus and thereby the absolute velocity and transport number of the indicator ion estimated with great accuracy. The method as it has been developed in the present paper enables the measurement of the mobility with precision without much trouble and furnishes more information regarding the changes that take place at the boundary than any other single apparatus devised up till now. The method can be used for students' experiments as the equipment can be easily got up.

In the previous measurements (Mukherjee, Mitra and Bhattacharyya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 177; Mukherjee, Mitra and Sen-Gupta, *ibid.*, 1936, **11**, 42) from this laboratory, a U-tube with three side-limbs (Fig. 1) a, b and c was taken. The boundary which is of the rising type was initially formed at XX' between a and b and its upward displacement (x) with time (t) was followed as electrolysis proceeded. The potential gradient in the upper electrolyte AR was measured by observing the potential, v_1 , between b and c and then dividing v_1 , with the effective length, l , between b and c. The velocity of the leading ion was calculated from the formula,

$$V_A = \frac{x}{l \cdot v_1 / l} \quad \dots (i)$$

The potential, v_2 , between a and b was also measured against the displacement, x , and the potential gradient in the indicator layer, P_m , was obtained from the relation

$$P_m = v_1 / l + dv_2 / dx. \quad \dots (ii)$$

The absolute rate of migration of the indicator V_B can then be obtained by dividing x/t by the potential gradient in the indicator.

When x was plotted against t , a straight line was obtained which tended to become convex towards the x -axis. v_2-x and v_2-t curves were not straight but showed a convex curvature towards the v_2 -axis, even at the beginning.

In the present arrangement the lowest side-limb was eliminated and the $x-t$ curve was obtained as a straight line. The v_2-x curve was found to be regular on forming the boundary initially at a place well below the side-limbs. The displacement of the boundary with time has been observed in the left limb of the tube which contains no side-limbs; while the potential measurements across the boundary have been carried out in the limb of the U-tube containing the side-tubes.

Greater care has been taken with regard to the following points than that in previous papers (*loc. cit.*):

(a) All the solutions have been prepared by direct weighing in a 2-litre volumetric flask instead of by the dilution of a stock solution.

(b) The potassium iodoosinate and potassium picrate used as the indicators have been recrystallised from conductivity water.

(c) The current has been taken from a battery of accumulator cells giving 110 volts.

(d) The current has been read with an ammeter reading directly up to 2×10^{-7} ampere and has been checked with a standard potentiometer.

(e) Reversible electrodes have been used.

(f) The specific conductivities have been measured more accurately with a Hartmann and Braun bridge using a valve oscillator of variable frequency as the source of the alternating current.

Sources of Error.—In the calculation of the transport number by the equation

Fig. 1.

Fig. 2.

$$T_A = \frac{v \cdot C_A \cdot F}{i \cdot t} \quad \dots (iii)$$

where v represents the volume traced by the boundary; C_A the concentration of the A ion; i , the current strength and t , the time; two types of corrections are necessary as has been indicated by Lewis (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, **32**, 862) and Longworth (*ibid.*, 1932, **54**, 2741). However these corrections amount to less than 0.1 in centinormal solutions and need not be discussed for the present case.

Constancy of Current.—In the measurements of McInnes and others (McInnes and Longworth, *Chem. Rev.*, 1932, **11**, 171; Hartley and Moilliet, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1933, **A140**, 141) a given length of the leading solution in the moving boundary tube is continuously displaced by the corresponding length of the less conducting indicator solution. The total resistance of the system therefore goes on increasing and in order to keep the current constant some external arrangement is necessary [*cf.* the elaborate constant current arrangement of McInnes and collaborators (*loc. cit.*) and the thermionic valve arrangement of Hartley and collaborators (Hartley and Donaldson, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1937, **33**, 457)]. With Mukherjee's cataphoretic apparatus, however, since the loss of conductivity in one limb is almost made up by the corresponding gain in the other, the current remains almost constant; hence an adjustment with a hand regulated rheostat serves the purpose.

Potential Gradient in the Leading Solution.

Since the concentration of the leading electrolyte above the boundary does not change with the progress of electrolysis, the potential gradient may in the same way either be directly determined or calculated from formula

$$P_{AB} = \frac{i}{K_{AB} \cdot Q} \quad \dots (iv)$$

where K_{AB} is the specific conductivity of the liquid AR and Q , the cross-section of the tube. The following table gives some of the results on the potential gradient of the upper liquid determined directly and indirectly from equation (iv).

TABLE I.

0.02N-KCl (Temp. 35°). $K = 0.003312$ mho. $l = 1.267$ cm. $Q = 0.2775$ sq. cm.

i (amp) $\times 10^{-6}$.	v_1 (obs).	P_{AR} .	P_{AR} (eq. iv)
925	1.287 volts	1.02 volts/cm.	1.01 volts/cm.
1100	1.515 1.518	1.12 "	1.12 "
1500	2.060	1.63	1.63

It is evident from Table I that the potential gradient in the upper electrolyte may be calculated from the current and cross-section of the tube without direct potentiometric measurements. This procedure was adopted for measuring the potential gradients in the leading solution in the present paper.

Reproducibility of Measurements.

The following table shows the reproducibility of results in a solution of 0.01N-KNO₃ with K₂I of suitable concentration as the indicator solution. It will be evident that the transport numbers do not diminish chronologically as in experiments previously reported (Mukherjee, Mitra and Bhattacharyya, *loc. cit.*; Mukherjee, Mitra and Sen-Gupta, *loc. cit.*).

TABLE II.

0.01N-KNO₃. Temp. = 35°. $i = 200 \times 10^{-5}$ amp. Sp. condty = 1632×10^{-6} mho.

Time.	Distance moved.	T_{NO_3} .	$V_{NO_3} \times 10^5$.
340 sec.	1.0 cm.	0.480	81.2 cm/sec.
511	1.5	0.479	81.0
681	2.0	0.480	81.2
849	2.5	0.480	81.2
1017	3.0	0.481	81.3

Limits of Adjustment of Concentrations.

Tables III—V contain the results on the transport number and absolute velocity measurements of the anions in centinormal potassium chloride, potassium nitrate and potassium sulphate solutions using various concentrations of potassium iodococinate as the indicator solution. The results are generally reproducible within about 0.3% when the concentration of the indicator solution is greater than that demanded by equation (v) (*vide infra*), when the indicator solution is more dilute the results are less reproducible. In Fig. 3 are plotted the transport numbers of the leading ions against the concentrations of the indicator, and in Fig. 4, the absolute rates of migration of the leading ions against the specific conductivities of the indicator.

TABLE III.

0.01N-KCl (sp. conductivity, 0.001697 mho). Temp. = $35^{\circ} \pm 0.05$.

Conc. of the indicator.	T_{Cl} (KCl).	$V_{Cl} \times 10^4$.	Conc. of the indicator.	T_{Cl} (KCl).	$V_{Cl} \times 10^4$.
0.00173N	0.499	87.8	0.00805N	0.504	88.6
	0.496	87.5		0.505	88.8
	0.499	87.7		0.501	88.1
	0.498	87.6		0.502	88.2
	0.498	87.6		Mean 0.503 $\pm$ 0.002	Mean 88.4 $\pm$ 0.35
	0.498	87.6			
	Mean 0.498 $\pm$ 0.0005	Mean 87.6 $\pm$ 0.15			
0.00464N	0.503	88.4	0.00337N	0.501	88.1
	0.504	88.6		0.504	88.6
	0.501	88.0		0.504	88.6
	Mean 0.503 $\pm$ 0.0015	Mean 88.3 $\pm$ 0.30		Mean 0.503 $\pm$ 0.0015	Mean 88.4 $\pm$ 0.25
0.00460N	0.525	92.3	0.00358N	0.537	97.4
	0.520	91.5		0.547	95.5
		Mean 91.9 $\pm$ 0.40		Mean 0.542 $\pm$ 0.005	Mean 96.4 $\pm$ 0.95

TABLE IV.

0.01N-KNO₃ (sp. conductivity = 0.001617 mho). Temp. = 35° ± 0.05.

Conc. of the indicator.	T_{NO_3} (KNO ₃).	$V_{\text{NO}_3} \times 10^5$.	Conc. of the indicator.	T_{NO_3} (KNO ₃).	$V_{\text{NO}_3} \times 10^5$.
0.0073 N	0.484	81.8 cm./sec.	0.485	82.0	82.0
	0.485	82.1	0.485	82.1	82.1
	Mean 0.485 ± 0.0005	Mean 82.0 ± 0.15			
0.0085 N	0.481	81.3 cm./sec.	0.00644 N	0.480	81.2 cm./sec.
	0.482	81.5		0.481	81.4
	0.483	81.8		0.484	81.9
	0.484	81.5		0.485	82.1
	Mean 0.482 ± 0.001	Mean 81.5 ± 0.25		0.484	81.9
				Mean 0.483 ± 0.002	Mean 81.7 ± 0.4
0.00557 N	0.500	84.5	0.00460 N	0.518	87.0
	0.499	84.5		0.532	87.6
	0.497	84.0			
	0.497	84.0			
	Mean 0.497 ± 0.0015	Mean 84.2 ± 0.25		Mean 0.520 ± 0.002	Mean 87.3 ± 0.3

TABLE V.

0.01N-K₂SO₄ (sp. conductivity = 0.001582 mho). Temperature = 35° ± 0.05.

Conc. of the indicator.	T _{SO₄}	V _{SO₄} × 10 ⁵ .	Conc. of the indicator.	T _{SO₄}	V _{SO₄} × 10 ⁵ .
0.01073 N	0.513	84.2 cm./sec.	0.00644 N	0.511	83.9 cm./sec
	0.509	83.5		0.509	83.6
	0.509	83.6		0.510	83.8
	0.513	84.2		0.510	83.8
	0.512	84.1		Mean 0.510 ± 0.001	Mean 83.8 ± 0.15
	0.510	83.6	0.00537 N	0.521	85.6
	Mean 0.511 ± 0.002	Mean 83.9 ± 0.35		0.523	85.8
0.00805 N	0.510	83.6		0.519	85.3
	0.512	83.8		0.521	85.6
	Mean 0.511 ± 0.001	Mean 83.7 ± 0.1		0.521	85.6
0.00403 N	0.541	87.7		Mean 0.521 ± 0.002	Mean 85.6 ± 0.25
	0.552	89.5			
	0.549	88.9			
	Mean 0.547 ± 0.005	Mean 88.7 ± 0.90			

* The above measurements have been carried out in collaboration with Mr. S. K. Mitra.

Fig. 3.

Curves 1-3 refer respectively to sulphate, chloride and nitrate.

Fig. 4.

DISCUSSION.

The results of various laboratories (*loc. cit.*) show a difference in the nature of adjustment curves. McInnes and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) working with falling boundaries have found that an adjustment is obtained only over a limited range of the indicator concentration on either side of which the results are vitiated. Hartley and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) on the other hand have found that with boundaries of the falling type quite reproducible results are obtained when the indicator solution has any concentration more dilute than that demanded by equation (v) (*vide infra*). The shapes of their curves are shown in Fig 5.

Fig 5.

The results of the present measurements, however, show that the range of adjustment is quite unlimited in the higher concentration range of the indicator since similar results have been obtained in the case of all the three electrolytes investigated. Similar observations were also made by Longworth (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 1897) with rising boundaries between KCl and KIO₃.

The curves may be explained in the following way after the method of Longworth (*loc. cit.*).

In Fig. 6 A and B are represented the two conditions, where the indicator concentration is respectively more concentrated and more dilute than the adjusted concentration. The following is the density relation between the indicator solutions :

Since in Fig 6A the lighter solution of the indicator is above the concentrated, the arrangement is left undisturbed, while in Fig. 6B the heavier solution of the indicator being above the lighter, the distribution is seriously affected by the difference in density. This will be more clear in the next section where we deal with the measurement of the indicator concentration behind the boundary.

The nature of adjustment curves is exactly similar in the case of the three electrolytes investigated including the weak nitrate ion and the polyvalent sulphate ion. The adjustment depends only on the concentration of the electrolytes and not on their specific electrochemical character.

Another point which may be mentioned is that the transport number increases linearly with C_2 , when C_2 is less than the adjusted concentration. This linear relationship remains as yet to be explained.

Concentration of the Indicator behind the Moving Boundary.

Cady and Longworth (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 1656) observed the increase in the total resistance in an autogenic moving boundary apparatus where a definite volume of the leading solution was displaced by the

indicator. They also measured the specific conductivity of the indicator solution behind the boundary with two platinised points. Both measurements showed within about 2% that the concentration of a solution behind a moving boundary adjusted itself according to equation (iii). The determination of C_m yields a means of calculating T_m^{23} and V_1 of the indicator ion.

Drew, Collie and Hartley (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1934, 30, 648) have, however, shown that the method cannot be applied in dilute solutions. They designed an apparatus giving what they called a balanced boundary in which the indicator solution behind the boundary can be continuously transferred to a side vessel and its conductivity determined there. Hacker (*Koll. Chem. Beih.*, 1935, 41, 147) has shown by external analysis as well as by potentiometric measurements that the relation of Kohlrusch and Weber (*Ann. Physik*, 1897, 62, 209; *Sitzungsber. Berlin Acad.*, 1897, 936) holds good.

In the previous communication from the laboratory (*loc. cit.*) the potential gradient in the indicator P_m was determined by equation (ii), as indicated before and V_1 was calculated from the relation $V_1 = \frac{x}{t \cdot P_m}$. The results however varied as much as 30% and were always higher than the accepted values.

The reason of this will be clear from the following consideration. The indicator BR (*cf.* Fig. 2) cannot be taken exactly at the adjusted concentration initially, it will be a little too concentrated or too dilute. Taking the latter case, the potential gradients along the cataphoretic tube may be represented by Fig. 7. Since C'_m is more dilute

than C_m the potential gradient in the former will be greater than that in the latter. The boundary was initially at XX' and with progress

of electrolysis has come to YY' and a volume of v of the leading solution AR has been displaced by the same volume of the indicator solution BR at the concentration C_{22} . If the potential V_2 between BB' and CC' is measured as the boundary moves then we have, $\frac{dv_2}{dx} = +P_{22} - P_{12}$, and adding P_{12} to the latter we get P_{22} . If, however, the potential is measured between AA' and CC' as in previous measurements (Mukherjee, Mitra and Bhattacharyya. *loc. cit.*; Mukherjee, Mitra and Sen Gupta. *loc. cit.*) we do not get P_{22} but any value between P_{22} and P'_{22} (potential gradient in C'_{22} solution). This then is the reason why the P. G. of previous measurements gave so erratic values of the absolute velocities of the indicator ion.

FIG. 8.

In the present investigation a narrow cataphoretic tube with two side-limbs, fused near each other, has been used. The boundary was

formed between 0.02N-KCl and various concentrations of potassium picrate. In Table VI are given the results of a particular set of measurements where the concentration of the indicator was 0.02N. Some of the results are also shown in Fig. 8.

TABLE VI.

Conc. of KCl = 0.02N. $K_{\text{rel}} = 3312 \times 10^{-6}$ mho. Conc. of $K_{\text{pic}} = 0.02N$.
 $K_{\text{pic}} = 2271 \times 10^{-6}$ mho Temp. = 35°. Current = 1100×10^{-6} ampere.

Time.	Potential.	Time.	Potential.
0 sec.	1.512 volts	2445 sec.	2.622 volts
300	1.512	2505	2.748
480	1.515	2780	3.072
940	1.515	2820	3.126
1395	1.521	3125	3.558
1700	1.572	3200	3.636
1755	1.596	3270	3.699
2160	2.148	3460	3.695
2195	2.211	3510	3.693

According to the theory of Kohlrausch (*loc. cit.*) and Weber (*loc. cit.*) which need not be recapitulated here the concentration of the indicator behind a moving boundary should be adjusted according to the relation,

$$C_A / C_B = T_A / T_B \quad \dots (v)$$

where C_A and C_B are the concentrations and T_A and T_B are the transport numbers of the leading and indicator ions respectively. It also follows from the relation that

$$V_B / V_A = P_{AB} / P_{BA} \quad \dots (vi)$$

where V_A is the absolute velocity of the leading ion and V_B that of the indicator ion, P_{AR} and P_{BR} being the two potential gradients.

Substituting the values of P_{AR} , P_{BR} and V_A in equation (vi) one gets the value of V_B as the following :—

$$V_{pic} = \frac{1.515}{3.693} \times 86.3 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm./sec.} = 35.4 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm./sec.}$$

Since the specific conductivities are inversely proportional to the potential gradients, the specific conductivity of the picrate solution behind the boundary is found to be

$$\frac{1.515}{3.693} \times 0.003312 = 0.001358 \text{ mho.}$$

The corresponding concentration is about 0.01195N.

$$\text{Applying equation (v) one gets for } T_{pic} = \frac{0.504 \times 0.01195}{0.02} = 0.301.$$

Table VIII gives the results of potentiometric measurements with 0.02N-KCl as the upper electrolyte and various concentrations of K_{pic} as the indicator electrolyte.

TABLE VII.

Conc. of KCl	Specific conductivity $\times 10^6$ of the soln. used.	Specific conductivity $\times 10^6$ behind the boundary.	$V_p \times 10^5$ cm./sec.
0.02 N	2271	1358	35.4
"	"	1357	35.4
0.0167	1889	1359	35.4
"	"	1359	35.4
0.0125	1418	1369	35.6

TABLE VIII (contd.).

Conc. of KP.	Specific conductivity $\times 10^8$ of the soln. used.	Specific conductivity $\times 10^8$ behind the boundary	$V_p \times 10^8$ cm./sec.
0.0125N	1418	1368	35.6
0.0111	1270	1419	36.9
"	"	1416	36.9
0.0105	1228	1523	39.6
"	"	1558	40.6

One can easily see from the results that when the indicator solution is more dilute than 0.012N, the specific conductivity of the solution behind the boundary is higher than the specific conductivity of the indicator at the adjusted concentration. This rise in the specific conductivity can only take place if some of the leading solution of higher specific conductivity comes inside the indicator layer.

The absolute velocities of the picrate ion obtained in this paper may be compared with that obtained by Ulich (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1927, 23, 388). He found the mobility of the picrate ion at infinite dilution to be 30.1 at 25° and $l_{p10} \times \eta$ to be 0.269, where η is the viscosity of the solvent. Dividing 0.269 with the value of η at 35°, i.e., 0.007208 poise (*Int. Crit. Table*, 1929, 8, 10) one gets 37.4 as the mobility at infinite dilution at 35°. From this value, the mobility of the picrate ion at a dilution of 0.012N at 35° may be calculated by applying Onsager's equation, and is found to be 34.1 and the corresponding absolute velocity to be 35.3×10^{-5} cm./sec. The value is in excellent agreement with the value of the velocity of picrate ion found by the author at a concentration 0.012N namely 35.5×10^{-5} cm./sec. Ulich (*loc. cit.*) also gives $l_{cl}' / l_{p10}' = 2.54$ at 25° and 2.20 at 100°. Taking the ratio to be 2.50 at 35° and the absolute velocity of the chlorine ion at 35° to be 83.3×10^{-5} cm./sec., in 0.01N solution, the absolute velocity of the picrate ion is found equal to 35.4×10^{-5} cm./sec.

S U M M A R Y.

1. The range of the concentration of the indicator, within which the

transport number and absolute velocity of the leading ion remains constant has been investigated in the case of KCl, KNO₃ and K₂SO₄.

2. It has been found that within the range of experimental accuracy namely about $\pm 0.3\%$ the transport number and absolute velocity remains constant when the indicator liquid is more concentrated than is demanded by the theory of Kohlrausch and Weber. Beyond this range the measured transport number and absolute velocity increases with the diminution in the concentration of the indicator.

3. The concentration adjustments in the indicator solution have been followed potentiometrically and it has been found that with concentrated indicator solutions dilute solutions of constant composition come out in every case. The absolute velocity and transport number of the indicator ion have been calculated from such measurements.

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PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY, CALCUTTA.

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